

Application of BIM for bridge monitoring

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Abstract

The application and integration of Building Information Modeling (BIM) into the realm of bridge monitoring represents a significant advancement in infrastructure management. This thesis explores the multifaceted implementation of BIM technologies for the purpose of monitoring and maintenance of bridges. It investigates how the integration of BIM technologies, specifically through the Dalux, can improve the way we monitor, manage, and maintain bridge infrastructure.

The thesis delves into the intricacies of BIM-enabled bridge monitoring, including coverage of aspects of data integration, real-time analytics, and decision support. It uncovers the transformative impact of 3D modeling, data visualization, and information exchange protocols in the realm of bridge management. Moreover, the research investigates into practical aspects of sensor deployment, data integration, and visualization within the Dalux platform. It explores how Dalux's user friendly interface empowers stakeholders to interact with 3D bridge models and it also addresses the collaborative potential of Dalux, emphasizing its role in bridging the gap between design, construction, and ongoing bridge management.

In conclusion, this thesis serves as a comprehensive guide to harnessing the power of BIM in bridge monitoring. It can be used by other professionals involved in bridge maintenance and management, such as engineers and stakeholders, contributing with methodologies and

advocating for the adoption of GIS (Geographic Information System) technologies in BIM integration.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/SoGMe2hZSgk>

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